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Contents

1. Introduction.....	3
Biocompatibility.....	3
Packaging.....	4
Structural design aspects.....	4
Summary.....	4
2. Circuits for Electrical Stimulation of Neural Cells.....	5
Power technologies.....	5
Communications.....	9
Architectures.....	9
Devices and Circuits.....	12
3. Circuit Architecture and Specifications.....	15
Signal specifications.....	15
Stimulation circuits.....	18
Global Device Architecture.....	24
4. Graphene Stimulation Electrodes.....	27
Organic electrodes.....	29
Graphene.....	30
5. Final Remarks.....	35
6. References.....	36

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the inception of the first implantable medical devices, in the late 50's of the last century, engineers had to face challenges related with materials, energy supply, functionality, size and communications.

The huge advances in key technologies enabled the successful development of many types of implantable medical devices, that in the meantime became common, such as pacemakers, real-time glucose meters, blood pressure sensors, cochlear implants, to name just a few.

The technological development in sensors, digital processing and transmission, electronics, miniaturization, information technologies, batteries and others, did not stop, enabling significant performance improvements on existing devices, as well as the use of technological solutions to deal with an increasing number of new health issues.

The inside of the human body is filled with electrical, chemical, mechanical, and chemical reactions, originating engineering challenges, e.g. related with electrical connectivity, communication and corrosion. Moreover, to preserve the patient's health, corrosion, robustness, hermeticity and electromagnetic emissions turn out to be key factors that have to be considered. In addition, processes that may occur in the body due to the presence of the implantable device have to be considered, such as the possibility of rejecting the device and developing inflammatory processes, that must be prevented at all cost.

As such, engineering implantable medical devices requires the consideration of several aspects that go beyond the simple technical functionality.

Biocompatibility

When medical devices are implanted, human body reacts to materials and contaminants, such as contaminant materials or microorganisms on the surface of the devices. Then, proteins may penetrate the materials and immune and inflammatory cells react to protect the human body (Onuki et al. 2008; Cameron et al. 1998). Thus, if the materials are not well matched with the tissues and cells, it may result in an unsafe effect on the body.

Therefore, proper biocompatible materials and suitable surface treatments must be used. Effective biocompatible materials include: titanium and its alloys, noble metals and their alloys, bio-grade stainless steels, some cobalt-based alloys and tantalum, to name just a few. Several references in the literature enumerate these materials e.g. (Schuettler et al. 2011; Antunes

and de Oliveira 2012; Witte 2010; Antunes and de Oliveira 2009; von Metzen and Stieglitz 2007; Catledge et al. 2002; Placko et al. 2000; Bundy 1994).

Packaging

Implantable medical devices require an effective protective barrier, to isolate them from the human body elements, e.g. cells, proteins and gases. The packaging also has to trap any substance (gases, liquids or solids) eventually produced by the electronic devices, preventing them to enter into the body, which could put human life in risk. A proper package thus should mutually isolate the electronic devices and the human body.

MIL-STD-883, Method 1014.10 was adopted by the medical device industry, detailing the hermeticity test procedures.

Packaging of implantable medical devices can be carried out with several materials, including quartz, fused silica, polymers, metals and ceramics e.g. (S.-J. Kim et al. 2012; Schuettler et al. 2010; Kazemi et al. 2004; Guenther et al. 2011).

Structural design aspects

Designing an implantable medical device goes far beyond the mere functional aspects, because the human body raises several constraints. For example, a device may meet the specified technical functionality, but if its size is excessive it cannot be used as an implant. This means that during the development process the trade-off between functional and non-functional properties must be always considered, for feasibility sake.

Active implantable medical devices, such as pacemakers and implanted blood pressure measurement devices, depend on energy supply for stimulation and eventually data processing transmission. The amount of energy can be significant and its source must be integrated with the electronic system. Batteries are the common solution, but its power density is still insufficient for long-term operation in some cases. Other power sources are under investigation (e.g. super-capacitors, energy harvesting), but the power budget is still one of the main constraints in the design of active implantable medical devices. Energy aspects are addressed in detail in a latter section of this deliverable.

Summary

Biocompatibility and packaging and key aspects to consider in the development of implantable electronic units. The literature reports the existence of several packaging materials that provide effective barriers between the electronic components and the human body. The kind of electronic components that shall be used in this project are common to other devices (micro-controller/DSP/ASIC, power supply, signal condition electronics, radio link), so standard packaging methods and materials should suffice to meet the project requirements. Power, size, shape, among other non-functional aspects, must be addressed during the design process in order to assure that the final product meets the requirements.

2. CIRCUITS FOR ELECTRICAL STIMULATION OF NEURAL CELLS

Power technologies

Flexible and biodegradable batteries

Batteries are the standard approach currently used to power most of the implantable medical devices, thanks to its high energy density, availability and robustness. Steady technological advances over the last decades consistently increased the battery's energy density, allowing to decrease its size and so extending the kind of medical devices in which they can be used.

New applications pose new requirements, such as flexibility and biodegradability, which promoted the development of new technologies.

Their main characteristics are a relevant power output, suitable for some types (low power) implantable devices. The natural degradation of Mg in aqueous solution is a challenge.

Table 1, based on (A. Kim et al. 2015), summarizes the characteristics of some of the more recent characteristics of flexible and biodegradable batteries.

Table 1: Flexible and biodegradable batteries' summary

Source	Type	Energy density
(Lu et al. 2014)	Flexible Li-ion LiMnPO ₄	135mAh/g
(Z. Wang et al. 2014)	Flexible alkaline CNT/PVA-PAA	236mAh/g
(Chen et al. 2014)	Flexible CNT/PEDOT:PSS	227mAh/g
(Chitnis, Tan, and Ziaie 2013)	Flexible paper-based Copper/ Hydrogel/Zinc	625 mA/m ²

(Yin et al. 2014)	Biodegradable Mg/PDMS/Mo, W of Fe	276 mAh/g
(Tsang et al. 2014)	Biodegradable Mg/MgCl ₂ /Fe	0,7mAh
(Y. J. Kim et al. 2013)	Ac(PGScin/AgNW)MNO ₂	9.58 mAh/g

Super-caps

Alternative power sources are super-capacitors, which allow storing relatively large amounts of energy. Although super-capacitors may outperform batteries in terms of power density, they tend to suffer from self-discharging, thus having a limited use lifespan.

However, new technologies, such as the incorporation of high-surface-area carbon-based materials enabled the development of super-capacitors with higher energy density, potentially allowing its use for implantable medical devices and, in particular, stimulation devices. Such super-capacitor types include electrostatic double-layer super-capacitors (EDLS) and Faradaic super-capacitors (FS). The first ones are based on charge accumulation while the other type is based on redox chemical reactions.

Table 2, based on (A. Kim et al. 2015), presents a summary of the characteristics of flexible super-capacitor technologies.

Table 2: Super-capacitor characteristics summary

Source.	Type	Capacitance or Energy density
(Fang and Binder 2006)	ELDC	100 F/g (4 22.5 mA/cm ²)
(Luo, Jang, and Huang 2013)	ELDC	100 F/g (@ 1 A/g)
(Yu et al. 2009)	ELDC	50-54 F/g
(S. Hu, Rajamani, and Yu 2012)	ELDC	115.83 F/g, 48.86 Wh/kg
(L. Hu, Wu, and Cui 2010)	ELDC	33 F/g, 250 kW/kg
(L. Hu et al. 2010)	ELDC	0.48 F/cm ²
(Yang et al. 2013)	ELDC	11 – 19.2 F/g
(Pech et al. 2010)	FS	1.3F/cm ³ , 1kW/cm ³
(Q. Wang et al. 2014)	FS	749 F/g (@ 0.5 A/g)

Energy scavenging

Energy scavenging is an attractive method that allows to generate power for the implanted devices during its use, unlike batteries and capacitors, that are storage elements, thus its operation lifetime is theoretically unlimited.

These kind of generators fall in two main types (piezoelectric and triboelectric), which use kinetic energy for generating electrical energy. Piezoelectric scavengers use body movements (e.g. walking, muscles moving members) to generate electrical charge by means of physical deformation of a material. Triboelectric scavengers use the movements to cause friction among two different dielectrics, thus generating charge.

Piezoelectric and triboelectric energy scavenging can be used to power implantable devices, but its energy density is small and the technology needs to be matured (Hwang et al. 2014). Moreover, the relatively small period of operation envisaged in this project turn energy scavenging unsuitable, so these power sources shall be no further considered.

Remote wireless powering

Remote wireless powering consists in using a (potentially unlimited) external power source to feed the implantable devices, without requiring trans-cutaneous wiring. The power density is smaller than with other technologies (e.g. batteries), but it is effective for low-power implantable devices, allows higher energy capacity than scavengers, and its lifetime is potentially unlimited, thus making it appealing.

The literature reports two main approaches: inductive and acoustic. There are works on the use of infrared light, but penetration constraints limit its use (Goto et al. 2001).

The most usual approach for remote wireless powering of implantable devices is inductive coupling, which consists on a near-field magnetic power transmission system, based on the induction Faraday's law. The performance depends on the self-inductance of the coils (primary and secondary), on their mutual inductance and on the quality factor (Q). These parameters are constrained by the small form factor imposed in implantable devices, which limits these parameters and consequently the energy transmission efficiency. Wireless inductive powering is suitable for implantable devices that allow sufficiently large coils (typically over 1 cm in diameter) placed close to the skin. (Yakovlev, Kim, and Poon 2012) provide a tutorial on the design of battery-less implantable devices, together with a model for the transmission from an external antenna to the implanted device antenna (Poon, O'Driscoll, and Meng 2010). A fundamental issue to guarantee the power transmission to the implantable device is the proper coupling between transmitter and receiver antennas, which varies with the biological subject. (O'Driscoll, Poon, and Meng 2009) propose tuning to be performed by matching the network comprised of a fixed inductance and a digitally controlled capacitor array. After reception, a rectifier is required to provide a DC voltage from the received AC signal. Self-Driven Synchronous Rectifier (SDSR) provide an adequate balance between input voltage and efficiency. A general overview of rectifier optimization can be found in (Mandal and Sarpeshkar 2007).

Other relevant and emerging methods for power transmission are based on acoustic/ultrasonic waves. These methods overcome some of the limitations of inductive powering that derive from the size constraints. Acoustic waves are omnidirectional and as such not sensitive to the alignment issues. As they operate at low frequencies (below 10MHz) the biological tissue absorption is not significant (penetrations up to 20 cm), although for smaller frequencies (tens of kHz) the receiver dimensions become unfeasible (too large).

Table 3 summarizes the main characteristics of recent wireless power transmission techniques.

Table 3: Wireless power transmission techniques

Source	Type	Eff.	Power	Freq.	Receiver size	Transmitter size/power	Distance Tx-Rx
(RamRakhyani, Mirabbasi, and Chiao 2011)	Multi-coil inductive	82%	NA	0.7 MHz	22 mm dia	64 mm dia	3.2 cm
(Ho et al. 2014)	Mid-filed inductive	NA	0.2 mW	1.6 GHz	2 mm dia	500 mW	5 cm
(Maleki et al. 2011)	Ultrasonic	NA	0.816 mW	2.15 MHz	1x5x1 mm ³	50*50*1 mm ³	10 cm
(Larson and Towe 2011)	Ultrasonic	NA	0.11 mW	1 MHz	1.33 mm dia	26 mm dia	12 cm
(A. Kim, Powell, and Ziaie 2014)	Acoustic	NA	1.098 uW	350 Hz	20*2*0.38 mm ³	11.665 W	15 cm
(Yakovlev, Kim, and Poon 2012)	Inductive	NA	NA	2 GHz	2 mm dia.	20 mm dia	5 cm

It is possible to combine remote wireless powering with local energy storage devices. This strategy allows improving the patient's comfort by allowing to avoid the permanent use of external charging devices. E.g. (Mendoza-Ponce et al. 2018) reports the use of super-caps that are charged when the implanted device is interrogated by the external reading unit. In this case a 81 seconds charge at 20 cm allows a full day of autonomy.

Summary

From the above analysis, it results that batteries or super-capacitors would be the natural candidates for powering the stimulation devices. The main reasons are the high energy density, the proven reliability and availability.

Wireless transmission shall also be considered, because the implantable devices to be developed in the scope of this project eventually may have, at least in some versions, a wireless link to communicate with the exterior, more specifically to receive configuration settings about the stimulus to apply. This opens the possibility of using the wireless link both to transmit signals and energy. The feasibility of this approach cannot be assessed now, as it will

ultimately depend on the type of stimulus to be applied, as well as on the characteristics of the wireless channel, which at the time of this writing are not yet sufficiently defined.

Communications

An implantable device, in most of the circumstances, will need to communicate with an external device. The implementation of the communication mechanisms must consider the power and size limits of the implantable device.

In (O'Driscoll, Poon, and Meng 2009), the authors propose the usage of mm-sized antennas due to its performance in biological tissue. For a greater efficiency, (Yakovlev, Kim, and Poon 2012) proposed the usage of asynchronous modulation schemes, that could reduce power consumption of data transceivers from tens of picojoules per bit in today's demodulators (Ghenim, Ghorbel, and Ben Hamida 2010) to sub-picojoule per bit.

Architectures

There is a trend towards the development of monitoring systems that are minimally invasive and that can be used during daily activities. This implies the use of wireless schemes to collect the data of implantable devices, thus avoiding the use of wires and cables.

Early techniques included simple schemes, such as the use of LC oscillators that had its oscillation frequency varying with biologic parameters such as temperature, pressure or pH (e.g. (Mackay 1959; Nagumo et al. 1962)).

The technical developments of digital microprocessors (miniaturization, processing power and energy efficiency) brought the possibility of using micro-controller-based digital communication architectures for signal acquisition and transmission of medical implanted devices with superior capabilities (Townsend and Arms 1996). Advantages include the capability of carrying out local processing of the signals, use robust digital transmission schemes, augment the number of signals, reconfigure the systems to tune and optimize its behavior, etc.

Digital telemetry platforms

(Valdastri et al. 2004) present the design and implementation of a digital, micro-controller based multi-channel telemetry system, targeting the acquisition and transmission of signals of different types of sensors on implantable medical devices. The device firmware is re-programmable and the system allows up to three different sensors. It employs a digital modulation scheme and error control mechanism to allow a reliable communication. The data is serialized and can be received by a PC's serial port, for persistence and visualization (via a GUI). Reduced power consumption was also a target design goal.

The characteristics of the device are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Device characterization (Valdastri et al. 2004)

Analog input channels	3
AD input	0...3V
AD conversion rate	25 ksamples/s
AD resolution	10 bits
Power supply	3V battery
Wireless link frequency	433.92 MHz ISM band
Data rate	Up to 40 kbps
Tx range	Up to 5m
Tx power	5.623 mW
Emitted power density	Up to 30 mW/m ²
Output format	RS232C
Error checking	Parity bit
Onboard memory	128 bytes, EEPROM
Lifetime	Up to 14 days
Size (unpacked)	18 mm * 9 mm * 5 mm
Size (with signal conditioning)	27 mm * 19 mm * 19 mm

The system comprises an implantable unit (based on Microchip PIC12 family micro-controller) that integrates a multiplexer, ADC, micro-controller, transmission unit and power supply. The system has an external unit (receiver unit) that has the RF link hardware (antenna and ASK receiver) and a RS232 interface, to connect to a PC. A GUI allows the user interaction with the system.

The selected carrier frequency and low transmission power (<30 mW/m²) are compatible with the international safety standards regarding electromagnetic field exposure.

(Natali et al. 2014) present a wireless platform targeting in vivo measurement of resistance properties of the gastrointestinal tract. The objective is to have a quantitative measurement of the propelling force that is required to move a capsule inside the gastrointestinal tract, without perturbing the physiologic conditions. To this end it is used a wireless transmission system, which in this case is based on a magnetically coupling between the capsule and an external permanent magnet. The platform estimates in real-time the axial magnetic force acting on the wireless capsule, which is manipulated by an external magnetic field, providing measurements of the capsule position, velocity, and acceleration.

The platform integrates the wireless capsule, the external permanent magnet and a PC, which is connected to a wireless transceiver via an USB port. The real-time data processing algorithms are executed on the PC.

The capsule integrates a permanent magnet, magnetic field sensors, a 3-axis accelerometer, a digital micro-controller, a wireless communication module and a battery-based power subsystem.

(Xie et al. 2017) present a portable digital wireless electrocorticography system aiming at the treatment of epilepsy. The system collects electrical signals of brain activities and stimulates the lesions. It integrates an high resolution array of flexible ElectroCorticography (ECoG) electrodes both to sense brain activities and to apply the stimulus.

As shown in Figure 1, the system is designed around a RHD2032 electrophysiology amplifier chip, specifically designed to acquire weak electrical signals from living tissue. This chip integrates the signal conditioning and acquisition electronics (amplification, filtering and a multiplexed 16 bit ADC), allowing up to 32 unipolar recording electrodes. Main characteristics include up to 30 kSamples/s per channel; low noise floor (2.4 μV rms typical), configurable lower and upper cutoff frequencies (0.1 Hz to 500 Hz and 100 Hz to 20 kHz, resp.) and integrated multi-frequency in situ electrode impedance measurement (intan TECHNOLOGIES, LLC 2012).

The RHD2032 chip has an SPI bus, which is used to interface with the exterior. In the case, a CC2541 SoC from TI is used, that features a Bluetooth® Low Energy and proprietary wireless MCU, which then communicates with a cellphone and with the cloud. Software running on these platforms decides about the necessity of applying stimulus.

Figure 1: Block Diagram of ECoG system

The system was used for carrying out ECoG system in-vivo testing. The electrode array was applied to the left primary sensory cortex of the rat brain. The normal rat brain signals have amplitudes lower than 50 μV , while when epilepsy episodes are induced signals have spikes that can exceed 150 μV . The system was able to record these signals, and show them on the cellphone. Data was also sent to a cloud where data mining and pattern recognition algorithms

were used to detect epilepsy incidents. Table 5 summarizes the system characteristics and compares it with similar Brain-Computer Interface systems.

	(Chin-Teng Lin et al. 2010)	(Hirata et al. 2011)	(Mestais et al. 2015)	(Bagheri et al. 2013)	(Tolstosheeva et al. 2015)	(Xie et al. 2017)
Type	EEG	ECoG	ECoG	EEG	ECoG	ECoG flexible
Sampling Frequency	512 Hz	1 kHz	1 kHz	1 kHz	25 kHz	30 kHz
Number of channels	1	128	64	256	124	32
Bandwidth	0.1–100 Hz	0.1–1000 Hz	0.5–300 Hz	1–5000 Hz	1–150 Hz	0.1–7500 Hz
Resolution	12 bit	12 bit	12 bit	N/A	N/A	16 bit
Input referred noise	N/A	2.8 μ V rms	1 μ V rms	7.99 μ V rms	N/A	2.4 μ V rms
Power consumption	3.7 V Li Battery	300 mW	75 mW	12.9 μ W	N/A	44.1 mW
Wireless Data rate	3 Mbps	400 kbps	450 kbps	N/A	N/A	2 Mbps
Wireless type	Bluetooth 2 + EDR	2.45 GHz	MICS band (402-405MHz)	ZigBee	N/A	BLE
Device size	4 × 2.5 × 0.6 cm ³ & 6.4 × 4.4 × 1 cm ³	2 × 3 × 0.25 cm ³ & 6 × 6 × 0.8 cm ³	5 cm diameter Antenna: 10 cm ²	30 × 22 × 15 mm ³	150 mm ²	1.8 × 2.4 × 1.1 cm ³

Table 5: Comparison of system characteristics with other Brain-Computer Interface systems (Xie et al. 2017)

Summary

The evolution and actual capabilities of digital technologies, namely in what concerns miniaturization, processing power and energy efficiency, turn them the more efficient platform for developing implantable devices, particularly when complex signal processing transmission are needed.

For this class of implantable devices, the typical architecture encompasses a complete instrumentation chain, including signal I/O, eventually with conditioning, a digital programmable processing element (microprocessor/micro-controller/DSP), a radio link and power supply. This architecture has several advantages with respect to the older analog implementations, namely by enabling local signal preprocessing, allowing the use of robust digital communication schemes, allowing processing a much higher number of signals and for being flexible and reconfigurable, thus allow to tune its behavior according with the specific, and eventually evolving, requirements of the application.

Devices and Circuits

(M. K. Kim et al. 2019) review recent trends and advances in neural network interface systems. Regarding probes, the paper states that different materials and strategies have been used over

time. Firstly tungsten micro-wires were used, followed by micro-fabricated silicon-based probes and arrays, which have been used both for in vivo small animal experiments (Michigan probe) and human implantation (Utah array) (HajjHassan, Chodavarapu, and Musallam 2008). These devices had electrodes with tens of micrometers and lengths of a few mm. However, these probes suffered from a mismatch on the Young's modulus with respect to the brain tissues, originating scars due to micro-motion, leading to an active research of alternative materials, such as polymer-based flexible neural probes (Luan et al. 2017). To cover wider brain regions, alternative shapes have also been developed, such as mesh (J. Liu 2018). One of the key aspects for recording biologic electrical signals is the electrochemical impedance at specific frequencies, 1 kHz for the case of the brain, conditioning the selection of materials for the electrode. These include gold (Au), platinum (Pt) and iridium (Ir), eventually complemented with electrodeposited conducting polymers to enlarge the effective surface and reduce the electrochemical impedance (Pranti et al. 2017). Significant efforts have been devoted to scale these systems to allow recording more signals. Currently, state-of-the art systems allow a few thousands of signals for in vivo applications (M. K. Kim et al. 2019).

Typical human-brain neural signals acquired by the micro-electrodes are action potential and local field potential with amplitudes that range from tens of microvolts to millivolts and a bandwidth of a few kHz. These signals are very weak, so its acquisition requires proper conditioning (amplification, filtering, and digitization) to allow minimizing the low-frequency noise. When considering a large number of signals, routing and power consumption become a bottleneck and several routing architectures have been proposed so far. For this project the number of signals is small, so this is not an issue.

(M. K. Kim et al. 2019) refer that there are three common stimulation modalities utilized in conjunction with neural recording: electrical, chemical, and optical stimulation. Electrical stimulation is the only one relevant to this project. For this case, micro-electrode arrays used for neural recording are also used for stimulation. The charge storage capacity (CSC), which is the total charge available at the electrode per unit surface area, and electrochemical impedance at the frequency of interest (1 kHz for individual neural spike recordings) are the two most important properties. The SNR depends on the CSC, so this parameter should be maximized. Electrodeposited Ir oxide is the most commonly used metal for stimulation electrodes, although other materials have been investigated. The treatment of the electrode surface with materials such as carbon nanotubes allows increasing the CSC. A new type of carbon electrode (glassy carbon) without any additional polymer coating process was reported to allow high CSC and reduced impedance at 1 kHz.

Regarding the electrode characteristics for electrical stimulation, paper (M. K. Kim et al. 2019) reports the following data:

Table 6: Electrode characterization

ELECTRODE MATERIALS	CSC (mC/cm ²)	CHARGE INJECTION LIMIT (mC/cm ²)	IMPEDANCE AT 1kHz (KΩ)	ELECTRODE SIZE(μm ²)	IMPEDANCE/ AREA (Ω/μm ²)
Au (electroplating)	3.18	~0.1	52	10000	5.2
Pt	6.26	0.026	—	—	—
TiN	2.35 (forward current)	0.87 (0.2 ms pulse)	—	4000	—
IrOx (electroplating)	25	—	7.1	2400	3
PtIr	1.2	0.15	26.6	17000	1.6
IrOx /Pt composite	46.28	—	—	—	—
ITO	0.058	—	—	8.5 (minimum)	—
Carbon nanotube fiber	372	6.52	14.1	1450	9.7
Graphene (doped and porous)	50	3.2	0.519	90000	0.006
PEDOT	75.6	—	23.3	177	132
Glassy carbon	61.4	3	5.8	70650	0.08

TiN: titanium nitride; IrOx: iridium oxide; ITO: indium tin oxide.

Electrical stimulation can take different forms: current-mode (Sooksood et al. 2011), voltage-mode (Rothermel et al. 2008; Bin Altaf, Zhang, and Yoo 2015) and charge-mode (Lee et al. 2015). Current-mode stimulation consists in feeding a pre-defined current to the electrode. As an advantage, this method allows an accurate control of the charge delivered to the patient. However its efficiency is poor, due to the required voltage headroom and uncertainty of the electrochemical impedance between tissues and the electrodes. Voltage-mode stimulation is more efficient, because the full voltage may be applied to the electrode, but it is difficult to control the amount of charge applied. Finally, by using a charge storage device (e.g. a capacitor) it is possible to have a tight control of the applied charge, with the issues related with current-mode stimulation. However, this approach requires dedicated per-channel external capacitors, which is a solution that does not scale, thus being viable only for a small number of channels.

Summary

Electrodes play a key role in monitoring and stimulation implantable medical devices. There are different kinds of materials that, in addition to be biocompatible, must have proper electrical characteristics, due to weak nature of the signals. Moreover, the materials to be used should also be suitable to take the shape of the implant structure. Graphene seems to be a suitable material. For this reason, a dedicated section of this deliverable is devoted to the literature review of this type of electrodes.

With respect to the stimulation methods, current- or voltage-mode are the primary methods that shall be considered, due to abundance of results reported in the literature that allow to derive specifications with some degree of confidence. However, charge-mode may be considered if the other methods do not reveal adequate, as the relatively low number of signals to apply does not preclude a priori the use of this method.

3. CIRCUIT ARCHITECTURE AND SPECIFICATIONS

Signal specifications

Table 7 summarizes the specifications for the stimulation signals that shall be developed in the scope of WP2. Some parameters are not yet defined at the time of writing this report. These require either further studies or decisions to be taken by the consortium, based partially in the information provided by this report.

Table 7: Signal characterization

1 Electrical Characteristics	In Vitro	Units	In Vivo	Units	Importance
1.1 Potentiostatic mode - voltage controlled					Must
1.1.1 Voltage range	0.1-25	V	0.1-25	V	Must
1.1.2 Voltage resolution	0,1	V	0,1	V	Must
1.1.3 Maximum Compliance current	200	uA	20	mA	Must
1.2 Galvanostatic mode - current controlled					Must
1.2.1 Current Range	1-200	uA	(TBD)-20	mA	Must
1.2.2 Current resolution	0,5	uA	TBD	mA	Must
1.2.3 Maximum Compliance Voltage	25	V	TBD	V	Must
2 Stimulus					
2.1 Shapes	Amplitude	Offset	Pulse Width	Duty-Cycle	
2.1.1 Square	V	V	V	V	Must
2.1.2 Triangular	V	V	V	X	Should
2.1.3 Ramp	V	V	V	X	Should
2.1.4 Sinusoidal	V	V	V	X	Should
2.1.5 Arbitrary					
2.2 Shape Timing Specifications	Resolution	Unit	Range	Unit	
2.2.1 Pulse Width	TBD	s	TBD	s	Must
2.2.2 Duty-Cycle	TBD	%	0-100	%	Must
3 Timing Specifications					
3.1 Modes	Shape Spec	#Pulses	Repetition Period		
3.1.1 Periodic	V	X	X		Must
3.1.2 Burst	V	V	X		Must
3.1.3 Pulsed	V	V	V		Must
3.2 Stimulus Timing Specifications	Spec.	Units			
3.2.1 Number of Pulses	1- (TBD)				Must
3.2.2 Repetion Period	0.1- (TBD)	Hz			Must
3.2.3 Timing Resolution	20	us			Must
4 Channel Characterization					
4.1 Number of Channels	16 Independent differential channels				Must
4.2 Device Operation Mode	Potentiostatic or Galvanostatic				Must
4.3 Multiplexing Strategy	TBD				Must

The table is organized in different categories:

- **Electrical characteristics:** specify the range, resolution and maximum value of the voltage/current to apply
- **Stimulus characterization:** define the signal shapes that shall be supported as well as the attributes that shall parameterize them
- **Timing specifications:** define the timing attributes of the signals, namely if they have some kind of periodicity or pattern
- **Channel characterization:** define the number of channels and their operation mode.

These values have been obtained from the literature survey presented in Deliverable 2.4.

The signals types and corresponding attributes are defined in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Signal shape and attributes

The basic pulse shapes are: Square, Ramp, Triangular and Sinusoidal

Each one of the shapes has one or more of the following attributes, which are sufficient to completely define them:

- **Amplitude** (X_a): amplitude of the signal, defined as the maximum difference between maximum (or minimum) value of the signal and its average value, except for the ramp signal, where it is defined as the difference between the maximum and minimum values.
- **Offset** (X_{off}): offset of the signal with respect to the reference/ground, defined as the average value of the signal.
- **Pulse Width** (T): time after which the basic pulse shape repeats
- **Duty-Cycle** (DC): ratio between the time the signal is on the high state and the pulse width (T_{on}/T)
- **Initial Value** $\{X(0)\}$: initial voltage/current value of the signal.

Signals are often applied repeatedly, forming different patterns. These attributes are depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Signal patterns

The considered timing modes are:

- **Periodic:** the basic shape, with pulse width T , repeats forever

- **Burst:** the basic shape, with pulse width T , is applied consecutively N times, during a time interval NT , and then stops permanently
- **Pulsed:** the basic shape, with pulse width T , is applied consecutively N times, during a time interval NT , and then stops. After a time W , the cycle repeats.

The following attributes allows to specify each one of the timing modes above:

- **Number of pulses (N):** number of consecutive pulses
- **Repetition period (W):** time duration after which the pattern repeats
- **Repetition duty-cycle (DC_W):** ratio $N \cdot T / W$

Stimulation circuits

The stimulation system shall have to generate several signals (voltage or current) that shall be applied to different electrodes, eventually at different times.

Moreover, stimulation and acquisition are interrelated processes:

- **Potentiostatic** (voltage mode) operation implies shared electrodes for stimulation and acquisition.
- **Galvanostatic** (current mode) operation allows independent electrodes for stimulation and acquisition.

As such, different combinations have to be considered:

- Current stimulation with differential reading
- Current stimulation with common electrode
- Voltage stimulation with common electrode

In what regards sampling, options are:

- Single multiplexed DAC/ADC
- Multiple DAC/ADC, eventually with synchronization

The following subsections present several circuits that allow to realize the stimulation and acquisition.

Basic circuits

Figure 4 shows the basic Galvanostatic/Current-mode circuit. The stimulation current (i_g) is controlled by the input voltage (v_g). The relation between them is given by $i_g = v_g/R$. In this figure, the amplifier in blue represents an instrumentation amplifier; operational amplifiers are represented in white.

Figure 4: Basic Galvanostatic/Current-mode circuit

The basic Potentiostatic/Voltage-mode circuit is depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Basic Potentiostatic/Voltage-mode circuit

The input opamp is set as a voltage-follower, applying the input voltage (v_g) to the cell.

In both cases the acquisition circuit allows to measure the input voltage.

Potentiostatic mode/voltage-mode

Type 1: multiplexed

An excitation signal is time-multiplexed and is applied to any given electrode pair (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Potentiostatic mode/voltage-mode: multiplexed

- Advantages:
 - Simplest hardware.
- Disadvantage:
 - Cells are not continuously excited;
 - Excitation occurs only in the multiplexed time slot;
 - Multiplexing may prevent the generation of the required signal patterns.

Type 2: continuous excitation

The excitation signal is fed in parallel to all electrodes, meaning that the same voltage signal is applied simultaneously to all cells. Each cell has its own current reading circuit (Figure 7). Multiplexing is performed after the reading circuit.

Figure 7: Potentiostatic mode/voltage-mode: continuous excitation

- Advantages:
 - Cells are continuously excited;
 - Multiplexing occurs by sampling the signal, without changing the conditions of the cell.
- Disadvantages:
 - Requires more hardware.

This circuit can be improved as follows (Figure 8):

Figure 8: Potentiostatic mode/voltage-mode: continuous excitation (improved)

In this case, the trans-impedance amplifier output is sampled. Having the sample control signal applied to all S&H circuits allows to synchronize the sampling instant on all channels.

Galvanostatic mode

The circuit for the Galvanostatic/current-mode excitation is shown in Figure 9. It is possible to sample the output voltage and synchronize the acquisition by means of a strobe signal

Figure 9: Basic galvanostatic/current-mode excitation circuit

By multiplexing the driving signal, it is possible to provide different excitation signals to the different cells (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Galvanostatic/current-mode excitation circuit: synchronous sampling and differential mode

Global Device Architecture

The implantable device will be centered on a digital processing element, or combination of elements, complemented with the signal conditioning electronics for signal stimulation and sensing. The device shall also include complementary functional blocks, namely a wireless link and a power management subsystem. The overall architecture is depicted in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Implantable device architecture

The electrodes and I/O interface depend on the kind of stimulation and signal acquisition to be employed. It shall be one of the circuits presented in the previous section.

The DAC/ADC module implements the interface between the digital processing element(s) and the analog signals applied/sensed by the electrodes. The resolution must be sufficient to satisfy the specifications. According with the actual knowledge, 12 bits shall suffice, but is possible to attain higher resolutions.

The digital processing element(s) block shall include at its core a micro-controller. The micro-controller shall run the firmware that generates the signal patterns, shall trigger the signal acquisition and process the data and, at the end shall send the collected data to the exterior via the wireless link. If the signal generation and/or signal processing become too complex, the system may include also digital co-processing elements, such as a Digital Signal Processor or an FPGA. These devices are able to carry out complex mathematical operations much more quickly and with higher energy efficiency than a general-purpose micro-controller.

The Digital Wireless link shall allow sending the collected data to the exterior, as said before, as well as modify the signal patterns to be applied, if necessary. The literature reports that commercial digital transceivers operating in one of the ISM bands allow sending several kbps, which is enough for the objectives of this project.

The Power subsystem is the block responsible for supplying energy to all the electronic components. It will include a battery and regulators to generate the required voltage levels. If the energy consumption of the implantable device combined with the duration of the stimulation experiments turn out to be too high, the battery can be replaced by a super-cap fed by an exterior unit.

As mentioned above, the implantable device has to upload the collected data to the outside, and eventually receive commands to parameterize the signal patterns that it should apply. As such, an external unit is required, to carry out the interface between both systems. Its architecture is as follows (Figure 12):

Figure 12: External unit architecture

A dedicated software application shall be developed for a PC. This application shall be able to store the collected data into a database, and allow the exploration of this data. The application will also have an interface that allows to parameterize the signals to apply, namely by setting the signal attributes defined in the beginning of this section (signal type, amplitude, offset, period, etc.).

The communication between the PC and the implanted device is carried out by a micro-controller coupled to the wireless transceiver that is the counterpart of the one integrated on the implanted device. The micro-controller will handle the wireless communication, implementing a protocol to handle errors and message validation. It will also communicate with the PC by means of an USB interface.

As shown in Figure 13, for the in vitro experiments the architecture is slightly different, as there is no need to have a wireless link.

Figure 13: In vitro global architecture

Up to the wireless link the blocks are exactly the same. The wireless link is in this case removed and replaced by an USB interface.

Although these solutions are similar from the architectural point of view, its realization is quite different, as the requirements differ substantially. For in vitro experiments there are no strict requirements in terms of power, size and weight. This simplifies significantly the implementation. Power can be obtained from the grid and thus is (potentially) unlimited. On the other hand, the processing block can be based on an embedded PC, providing processing power and memory that are several orders of magnitudes higher than the ones allowed by micro-controllers.

4. GRAPHENE STIMULATION ELECTRODES

Several lines of research are currently directed towards the development of advanced electrodes that can be reliably safe and sensitive. The amount and diversity of such electrodes seem almost unlimited since different applications demand different electrode types with respect to their size, invasiveness, selectivity, materials and performance.

For every electrode there is an intrinsic charge injection capacity (CIC), restricting the voltage that can be safely generated at the electrode's surface. Beyond this electrochemical limit, also known as the water-window, irreversible electrolysis of water can result in tissue damage, electrode dissolution, pH variations and production of unwanted species (Aryan, Kaim, and Rothermel 2015; Harris et al. 2018; Wellman et al. 2018).

To generate an effective electrical stimulation, it is crucial to select new electrode geometries/sizes, materials and/or coatings in order to increase the charge transfer surface area such that the charge injection safety limits are preserved.

Biocompatible, corrosion resistive materials for electrical recording and stimulation include gold, titanium, tungsten, platinum, iridium oxide, stainless steel, alloys of the mentioned metals, highly doped semiconductors such as silicon, and conductive polymers. Lately, several electrodes have been improved by modification of the surface chemistry with carbon-based coatings, as well as with biological ones (Y. Kim and Romero-Ortega 2012).

The current development towards smaller electrodes to improve spatial resolution present another set of problems, as they must withstand a higher voltage to transport the same charge per area than a larger electrode in order to induce the same response (Harris et al. 2018). Smaller electrodes enhance the applied charge density, as they inevitably suffer from high electrical impedance and consequent high thermal noise, leading to potential tissue damage and of the electrodes themselves, and thus deteriorating the signal-to-noise ratio (Aryan, Kaim, and Rothermel 2015; Boehler, Stieglitz, and Asplund 2015).

The most well-established type of electrodes consists of an assembled array of metallic (gold, platinum, and titanium) microelectrodes (10-200 μm in diameter), fabricated by complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (CMOS) technology, passivated (to work in a liquid environment) and connected to an external measurement unit – the so-called MicroElectrode Array (MEA). MEAs have been studied for decades and are typically fabricated on rigid substrates (e.g., quartz, silicon, sapphire, glass, etc.) and difficult to combine with soft tissue, due to their high mechanical mismatch. A specific type of MEAs that have been used as

stimulation electrodes, as well as for the recording of an electroneurogram in the area of functional electrical stimulation are the multielectrode cuffs. Cuff electrodes have an established story for long-term recording of neural activity – up to 63 weeks after implantation in human volunteers (Fisher et al. 2009). Cuff electrodes typically enclose the nerve with flexible and self-sizing silicone or polyimide that avoid stretching or compression damage of the enclosed nerve. On the other hand, when two individually addressable microelectrode array strips are integrated onto the same plane with an interdigitate approach, they are designated as planar InterDigitated Electrodes (IDE) (Ahadian et al. 2012; Lim et al. 2013; Z. Liu et al. 2017). This type of electrodes generates stimulation under low voltage and in a direct, effective, highly reproducible and controlled manner. IDEs are widely utilized in technological applications, particularly in the field of biological and chemical sensors due to their inexpensiveness, ease of fabrication process and high sensitivity.

MEA are part of a group of peripheral nerve interfacing (PNI) electrodes. In fact, PNI can be both extraneural (e.g. Cuff electrodes) or intraneural (e.g. MEA).

Intraneural electrodes are placed directly in the peripheral nerves and their proximity provides increased neural selectivity and sensitivity. According to the specific mode of intraneural electrode placement within the nerve tissue, the scientific community recognizes four major electrode designs (Y. Kim and Romero-Ortega 2012):

- 1) Longitudinally Implanted Intrafascicular Electrodes (LIFE) – limitations include drift in the population of cells being recorded and a decrease in signal-to-noise ratio over time;
- 2) Transverse Intrafascicular Multi-channel Electrodes (TIME) – which penetrates the peripheral nerve and is designed to selectively activate different fascicles within the nerve;
- 3) Coiled Wire Intrafascicular Electrodes (CWIE) – made from nylon-coated stainless steel wire and is wound into helical flexible coils to allow for expansion and contraction within the surrounding nerve tissue; and
- 4) Utah Slanted Electrode Array (USEA) – a version of MEA but made of needle electrodes of varying lengths (0.5 to 1.5 mm with 0.1 mm difference in length between rows of neighboring electrodes) designed to access most fascicles within the nerve.

A specific subset of intraneural PNIs are regenerative electrodes, which are based on an alternative design to penetrating electrodes and are used for the spontaneously regrowth of peripheral nerves after injury. In general, the sensitivity of regenerative electrodes is superior to that of extraneural electrodes. However, their implantation requires invasive surgery, which might be justified in most amputee cases (Y. Kim and Romero-Ortega 2012). There are three types of regenerative electrodes:

1. Sieve electrodes – can be either ring or needle shaped placed between two ends of the cut nerve. Can originate nerve compression injury.;

2. Regenerative Multielectrode Interface (REMI) – placed between the transected ends of an end-to-end repaired nerve. Does not restrict the growth of the nerve, and thus the nerve compression injury typically observed for Sieve electrodes does not occur.
3. Microchannel Roll Electrode (MCRE) – rolled into a 3D channel bundle and designed to fit the transected peripheral nerve at both ends of the roll.

All the above mentioned PNI suffer from limitations, particularly in terms of safe reliability, as well as sensitivity. (Y. Kim and Romero-Ortega 2012) distributed the different types of PNI according to their sensitivity and invasiveness (see Figure 1). For the authors, sensitivity is related to the electrode's ability to record action potentials, while invasiveness relates to the damage to the nerve while placing the electrode.

Figure 14: Different types of PNI according to their sensitivity and invasiveness (Y. Kim and Romero-Ortega 2012)

The purpose of this section is to describe the use of graphene electrodes, taking into consideration a set of important features that may interfere with the cell stimulation when using electrical fields, namely: composition; configuration, such as area; format (MEA, interdigitated or spiral cuff) or shape (3D scaffold hybrids). A summary of the systems addressed is then presented on Table 1. Other types of electrodes are discussed in detail in Deliverable D2.4.

Organic electrodes

In particular, the use of carbon allotropes (like carbon nanotubes, graphene, etc.), and conductive polymers (like Polypyrrole, PEDOT, Polyaniline, etc.) have shown that tailored approaches can be used to create microelectrode arrays (MEA) which not only improve the electrode material properties, but also provide biomolecules to aid in the establishment of a

chronically stable neural interface. Organic coatings hold a significant benefit over the inorganic coatings as they can be easily modified to include functional molecules to influence the biological behaviour (Aregueta-Robles et al. 2014).

Graphene

Graphene has many promising features such as biocompatibility, intrinsic flexibility and excellent electrical properties, allowing applications in the high-frequency regime. In some cases, the transparency of graphene also provides possibilities for the development of new tools for optogenetics (Kireev et al. 2016; Kuzum et al. 2014; Park et al. 2014). Researchers have only recently begun to investigate graphene and its derivatives as potential scaffolds for neuronal growth. Graphene has attracted a generalized interest due to its excellent conductive properties, but also because its nanostructure and its chemical stability render it a good candidate for favoring cell adhesion (Monaco and Giugliano 2014). In vitro studies, carried out on human cell lines (i.e., HepG2, BEAS-2B, PC12, hMSCs), have demonstrated that the cyto- and genotoxicity of graphene depends on the dose, shape, and size of the nanomaterial itself, as well as on the presence of metal contaminants, oxides and/or residues of the graphene oxidation (graphene oxide) preparation method in samples.

For instance, the surface charges on graphene substrates has been investigated by (Tu et al. 2014), who cultured primary rat hippocampal neurons on carboxylated GO (GO-COOH; negative surface charge; control condition), the surface of which had been chemically modified by functionalization with three functional groups: methoxy (-OCH₃; nearly neutral surface charge), amino (NH₂; positively charged surface) and poly-m-aminobenzene sulfonic acid (-NH₂/-SO₃H, PABS; zwitterionic). Although no relevant differences in morphology were observed, neurons cultured on a positively charged surface showed a greater number of neurites per neuron, a longer length of neurites and a greater number of branches per neurite.

The use of graphene as an in vitro or an in vivo stimulator device was the primary focus of a study conducted by (Heo et al. 2011), who developed a graphene/PET film to test the effects of a non-contact field stimulation on cell-to-cell coupling. This film was found to be biocompatible and improved SHSY5Y human neuroblastoma cell proliferation and viability compared to those observed in the control cultures. A transient non-contact electric field was produced by charge-balanced biphasic stimuli through the graphene/PET film electrodes and applied to cultured neural cells. We found that weak electric field stimulation (pulse duration of 10 s) as low as 4.5 mV/mm for 32 min was particularly effective in shaping cell-to-cell interaction.

The differentiation into neurons of human neural stem cells (hNSCs) cultured on graphene has been studied by (Park et al. 2014). The results shared by the authors showed not only an improved differentiation but also an enhanced cell adhesion and neurites formation compared to control conditions. A series of voltage pulses (usually, 1 ~ 10 of 500 mV monophasic/cathodic voltage pulses with 1 ~ 100 ms duration in a second) were applied to the differentiated cells via the graphene electrodes.

(Li et al. 2013) designed a three-dimensional (3D) graphene foam scaffold for neural stem cells (NSC). This scaffold allowed the formation of a three-dimensional neural network, resulting in an excellent substrate for cell adhesion and proliferation by up-regulating Ki-67 protein expression. To test whether such a scaffold could be used as a neural stimulation electrode, its electrochemical properties were investigated by cyclic voltammetry. The results showed that electrical stimulation via a capacitive charge injection was enhanced (due to the larger specific surface area of the 3D scaffold) compared to the use of conventional graphene film electrode.

(Kireev et al. 2016) prepared a graphene microelectrode array (GMEA) with 20 μm diameter on a flexible polyimide substrate. Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy using graphene as working electrode and Ag/AgCl pellet as reference electrodes in PBS solution was studied. PBS was used as electrolyte to mimic physiological condition in vivo. A 10 mV alternating current (AC) potential was applied and a frequency range between 1 Hz and 1MHz was scanned in order to perform extracellular recordings by measuring electrical activities from acute heart tissue and cardiac muscle cells (cardiomyocyte-like cells, HL-1). The impedance of GMEA measured at 1kHz was around $1 \pm 0.5 \times 10^5 \Omega$. The results showed good signal-to-noise ratios for both heart tissue and HL-1 cells. (Gomes et al. 2019) also fabricated a GMEA (composed of graphene microelectrodes with TiN tracks and contact pads) and reported a mean value of charge injection capacity of 0.7 mC/cm², which they claimed to be a satisfactory value and higher than the amplitudes obtained for MEAs reported in the literature. To determine if the GMEA worked properly, the authors used Electrical Impedance Spectroscopy and applied a sinusoidal excitation between 10 and 50 mV of unit frequency (<1 to 105 Hz). The produced GMEA exhibited an average impedance at 1 kHz of 5.2 k Ω . (Gomes et al. 2019) compared their results with previous studies for graphene electrodes. For instance, they cited that the 0.31 mm² electrodes prepared by (Körbitzer et al. 2019) with pure gold, graphene on gold and graphene/SiO₂, found a CIC of 0.03, 0.2 and 0.8 mC/cm², respectively. Moreover, at frequencies between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance values found were 7 k Ω , 4.4 k Ω , and 10 k Ω , for gold, graphene on gold, graphene/SiO₂, respectively.

(Du et al. 2015) reported the impedance of MEAs with graphene and with gold electrodes (20 μm diameter) tested at frequencies between 0.1 and 100 kHz, showing higher impedance values than the ones observed by (Gomes et al. 2019) and (Körbitzer et al. 2019): 170 k Ω for the graphene electrode and 186 k Ω for the gold electrode.

In a different work, (Koerbitzer et al. 2016) prepared 3 different MEAs with an electrode size of about 700 μm^2 . Gold, graphene on a thin gold layer, and plain graphene were fabricated on borosilicate glass substrates. Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 2.3 M Ω and 0.88 M Ω for plain graphene and graphene on gold, respectively. Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons. Neuronal recordings showed enough signal-to-noise ratio for both electrodes and a stable impedance. Stimulation measurements yielded a CIC of 0.15 mC/cm² using biphasic pulses of 1 ms and 1 μA for transparent graphene electrodes. (Koerbitzer et al. 2016), cited other authors, namely (Park et al. 2014; Kuzum et al. 2014; Kireev et al. 2016), who also studied different size graphene electrodes (from 310000 to

314 μm^2), on different substrates (polimide, Parylene-C, quartz glass and borosilicate glass) and then with different impedances.

Table 8- Summary of graphene-based systems used for electrical stimulation.

System	Electrical conductivity	Biocompatibility Study	Electrical Stimulation Paradigm	Additional Notes	Ref.
Graphene	N.A.	human neural stem cells (hNSCs) for brain repair and neural regeneration	1 ≈ 10 of 500 mV monophasic/cathodic voltage pulses with 1 ≈ 100 ms duration in a second	Graphene grown by CVD and then transferred to glass slides and coated with laminin	(Park et al. 2014)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural stem cell (seeded with a density of 5x10 ⁴ cells/mL)	monophasic cathodic pulses were applied, and the stimulation threshold was 20–30 mA	3D graphene foam synthesized by CVD method with Ni foam as template	(Li et al. 2013)
Graphene	N.A.	Extracellular recordings by measuring electrical activities from acute heart tissue and cardiac muscle cells (cardiomyocyte-like cells, HL-1)	The impedance of GMEA measured at 1kHz was around 1±0.5 x 10 ⁵ Ω	Graphene microelectrode array (GMEA) with 20 μm diameter on a flexible polyimide substrate	(Kireev et al. 2016)
Graphene	N.A.	dorsal root ganglion neuron of Wistar rats	Sinusoidal excitation between 10 and 50 mV of unit frequency (<1 to 105 Hz). The produced GMEA exhibited an average impedance at 1 kHz of 5.2 kΩ.	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with TiN tracks and contact pads.	(Gomes et al. 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.2 mC/cm ² . Between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 4.4 kΩ.	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with graphene on gold	(Koerbitzer et al. 2016)
Graphene	N.A.	cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.8 mC/cm ² . Between 1 Hz and 1 MHz, the lowest impedance value found was 10 kΩ.	0.31 mm ² electrodes. GMEA with graphene/SiO ₂	(Koerbitzer et al. 2016)

System	Electrical conductivity	Biocompatibility Study	Electrical Stimulation Paradigm	Additional Notes	Ref.
Graphene	N.A.	rat cortical neuron	Impedance tested at frequencies between 0.1 and 100 kHz was 170 k Ω	20 μ m diameter electrodes. GMEA with graphene on gold	(Du et al. 2015)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 0.88 M Ω .	Graphene on a thin gold layer fabricated on borosilicate glass substrate. Electrode size 700 μ m ² .	(Körbitzer et al. 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	Neural cell culture was performed using cryo-conserved embryonic cortical rat neurons	CIC of 0.15 mC/cm ² using biphasic pulses of 1 ms and 1 μ A for transparent graphene electrodes. Impedance studies at 1 kHz revealed a value of 2.3 M Ω .	Graphene on a thin gold layer fabricated on borosilicate glass substrate. Electrode size 700 μ m ² .	(Körbitzer et al. 2019)
Graphene	N.A.	SHSY5Y human neuroblastoma cells (3x10 ⁵ cells in a 30 mm culture dish)	A transient non-contact electric field was produced by charge-balanced biphasic stimuli. Weak electric field stimulation (pulse duration of 10 s) as low as 4.5 mV/mm for 32 min was particularly effective in shaping cell-to-cell interaction	Graphene grown by CVD and transferred to a PET film	(Heo et al. 2011)

5. FINAL REMARKS

This report addressed the issues related to the design of the electronic controller for the system to be developed, providing a state-of-the-art review on the up to date proposals found in the literature. The topics covered in this review cover the components and devices to power the system, the communications system to carry information to and from the implantable device, the architectures and the specific devices and circuits to interface with the organism. The power technologies considered include both on-device storage, such as batteries or super-caps, and processes to collect energy from the surroundings, such as energy scavenging and wireless powering.

In what concerns the circuit architecture and specifications, the specifications for the excitation signals were defined. The proposed solution covers what is expected to be the range of possible signals to be applied in order to stimulate cell growth. Some of the parameters are still undefined, as they depend on decisions to be taken in the future. The proposals include also the circuits that will generate these signals, considering both galvanostatic and potentiostatic approaches. The proposed device architecture is presented at the end of Section 3.

Finally, the topic of the electrodes is addressed in section 5. Intra-neural electrodes assume a particular importance here, given the scope of the project and, in particular, regenerative electrodes. Our study addresses both organic and graphene based electrodes, providing a comparison of several graphene based solutions found in the literature.

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